

Heather pollen is not necessarily a healthy diet for bumble bees

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This paper has been peer-reviewed and received a PCI Recommendation available here:

Recommendation citation:

Ignasi Bartomeus (2023) The importance of understanding bee nutrition. *Peer Community in Ecology*, 100534. doi: [10.24072/pci.ecology.100534](https://doi.org/10.24072/pci.ecology.100534)

Cite this paper version as: Tourbez, C., Semay, I., Michel, A., Michez, D., Gerbaux, P., Gekière, A. & Vanderplanck, M. (2023). Heather pollen is not necessarily a healthy diet for bumble bees (Version 3). Peer-reviewed and recommended by Peer community in Ecology. Zenodo. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8271044>,

35 **ABSTRACT**

36 There is evidence that specialised metabolites of flowering plants occur in both vegetative
37 parts and floral resources (i.e., pollen and nectar), exposing pollinators to their biological
38 activities. While such metabolites may be toxic to bees, it may also help them to deal with
39 environmental stressors. One example is heather nectar which has been shown to limit
40 bumble bee infection by a trypanosomatid parasite, *Crithidia* sp., because of callunene
41 activity. Besides in nectar, heather harbours high content of specialised metabolites in pollen
42 such as flavonoids but they have been poorly investigated. In this study, we aimed to assess
43 the impact of *Crithidia* sp., heather pollen and its flavonoids on bumble bees using non-
44 parasitised and parasitised microcolonies fed either control pollen diet (i.e., willow pollen),
45 heather pollen diet, or flavonoid-supplemented pollen diet. We found that heather pollen
46 and its flavonoids significantly affected microcolonies by decreasing pollen collection as well
47 as offspring production, and by increasing male fat body content while parasite exposure had
48 no significant effect except for an increase in male fat body. We did not highlight any
49 medicinal effect of heather pollen or its flavonoids on parasitised bumble bees. Our results
50 provide insight into the impact of pollen specialised metabolites in heather-bumble bee-
51 parasite interactions. They underline the contrasting roles for bumble bees of the two floral
52 resources and highlight the importance of considering both nectar and pollen when
53 addressing medicinal effects of a plant towards pollinators.

54
55 **Keywords:** Plant-pollinator interaction, Pollen specialised metabolite, Microcolony performance,
56 Bumble bee health, Parasite

57 **Introduction**

58 For their own subsistence and that of their offsprings, bee females mostly forage on two floral
59 resources, namely nectar as main source of carbohydrates (Nicolson & Thornburg, 2007), and pollen as
60 main source of proteins and lipids (Campos et al., 2008). Among these nutritional resources, the pollen
61 chemical composition is particularly complex and highly variable among plant species (Vaudo et al., 2020).
62 While pollen central metabolites, for instance, the protein-to-lipid ratio, play a crucial role in bee health,
63 development, and fitness (Di Pasquale et al., 2013), pollen also contains numerous specialised metabolites
64 (e.g., alkaloids, flavonoids and terpenoids, Irwin et al., 2014; Palmer-Young et al., 2019). The biological
65 activities of these metabolites are multiple so that they may be involved in protecting pollen from abiotic
66 factors, such as UVs (Li et al., 1993), but also from biotic factors, acting as antibacterial, antifungal or
67 insecticidal compounds (Pusztahelyi et al., 2015; Zaynab et al., 2018). When ingesting pollen, bees are then
68 exposed to all these biological activities that may be beneficial, for instance by reducing parasite load
69 through antimicrobial activities (Manson et al., 2010; Biller et al., 2015; Richardson et al., 2015), but also
70 detrimental, for instance by impairing resource collection (Wang et al., 2019; Brochu et al., 2020),
71 decreasing offspring size and production (Arnold et al., 2014), inducing larvae or imago death (Hendriksma
72 et al., 2011; Weber, 2004), and altering immune system (Gekière et al., 2022a). Given these opposite
73 effects on bees, it is essential to question how specific specialised metabolites may impact bee health,
74 especially in a changing world with multiple environmental pressures.

75
76 In the current context of biodiversity erosion (Butchart et al., 2010), bees are unfortunately no
77 exception, and many threats have been pinpointed as responsible for their negative population trends
78 (Dicks et al., 2021) such as pesticide exposure (Sánchez-Bayo & Goka, 2014), metalloloid pollution (Gekière
79 et al., 2023), habitat loss (Baude et al., 2016), resource scarcity (Naug, 2009), competition with
80 domesticated species (Mallinger et al., 2017), and diseases (Van Engelsdorp et al., 2009). Among
81 environmental challenges, bees indeed suffer from a high diversity of pathogens and parasites (Meeus et
82 al., 2011; Goulson & Hughes, 2015) of which effects vary from small ethological alterations of minor

83 consequences (Paris et al., 2018) to large reductions in host bee fitness (McMenamin & Genersch, 2015).
84 Social bee species such as bumble bees (Apidae; *Bombus* spp.) are particularly impacted by parasites, the
85 latter benefiting from their social system to readily infect numerous individuals (Folly et al., 2017). One of
86 the most prevalent parasites in wild bumble bee populations is the gut trypanosomatid *Crithidia bombi*
87 Lipa & Triggiani, 1980 (Euglenozoa: Trypanosomatidae; Schmid-Hempel, 2001). Despite its generally
88 moderate impacts, it can decrease foraging effectiveness (Otterstatter et al., 2005), offspring production
89 (Schmid-Hempel, 1998), queen survival through hibernation (Fauser et al., 2017), and increase mortality in
90 synergy with other stresses (Brown et al., 2000). To deal with such parasite pressure, bumble bees may
91 rely on specific floral resources displaying appropriate antimicrobial properties through their specialised
92 metabolites (Manson et al., 2010; Biller et al., 2015; Richardson et al., 2015; Fitch et al., 2022).

93
94 Among potential medicinal floral resources, the heather (*Calluna vulgaris* Hull. 1808), an Ericaceae
95 commonly foraged by bumble bees (Descamps et al., 2015), produces a nectar documented to affect *C.*
96 *bombi* (Koch et al., 2019). This effect has been attributed to the presence of callunene, a terpenoid that
97 induces the loss of *C. bombi* flagellum, preventing the parasite from settling in the bumble bee digestive
98 tract (Koch et al., 2019). Such medicative properties of heather nectar make heather-rich heathlands even
99 more valuable for these bumble bees (Descamps et al., 2015; Moquet et al., 2017). However, although
100 heather is a major resource for European bees, only a handful of studies have sought for specialised
101 metabolites with biological activities in heather pollen, showing a high prevalence of flavonoids (Gekière
102 et al., *in prep.*). Flavonoids can have very contrasting effects on insect-plant interactions and affect them
103 in multiple ways (Simmonds 2003; Onyilagha et al., 2012). Bees are attracted to some flavonoid compounds
104 (e.g. quercetin; Liao et al. 2017a) while others repel them (e.g. kaempferol, catechin; Detzel & Wink 1993;
105 Onkokesung et al., 2014). However, despite some deleterious effects on larval development (Wang et al.,
106 2010), flavonoids are mainly not toxic molecules for insects (Detzel & Wink, 1993). Once ingested,
107 flavonoids can have antioxidant properties and are potentially beneficial for bees (e.g. quercetin; Treutter,
108 2005). They can stimulate the activation of detoxification enzymes (cytochrome P450 monooxygenase) and
109 enhance bee resistance to certain insecticides and acaricides (Scott et al., 1998; Johnson et al. 2012; Liao
110 et al., 2017b). The case of heather pollen flavonoids remains to be addressed and this incomplete picture
111 of the pollen side does not allow for fully arguing that heather is a bumble bee health-promoting plant.
112 Therefore, bioassays to determine heather pollen effects on bumble bee brood, bumble bee health, and
113 parasite dynamics are warranted. To fill this gap, we herein present a study that aimed to assess the effects
114 of heather pollen and its flavonoids on bumble bee health, at both individual and colony levels, considering
115 the bumble bee interaction with the parasite. We specifically addressed the following questions: (i) how
116 does the parasite influence the development of bumble bee microcolonies and individual
117 immunocompetence? (ii) do heather pollen and its flavonoids challenge bumble bees, impacting their
118 resource collection and offspring production? (iii) do heather pollen and its flavonoids affect the parasite
119 dynamic in infected bumble bee workers, or help bumble bees to counteract parasite effects? We expect
120 (i) a mild effect of the parasite on bumble bees reared in optimal conditions; (ii) detrimental effects of
121 flavonoids, and potentially of heather pollen on healthy bumble bees and microcolonies; and (iii) beneficial
122 effects of heather pollen, and potentially its flavonoids, on infected bumble bees by reducing parasite load.

123 **Materials and methods**

124 **Bumble bee bioassays**

125 Queenless microcolonies of five workers were exposed to specific diet treatments (Fig.1): control pollen
126 (i.e., willow pollen is used because artificial pollen is unsuitable for bumblebee development and because
127 its flavonoid profile does not overlap with any flavonoids found in heather pollen; Gekière et al., 2022b;
128 Gekière et al., *in prep*) containing either (i) parasitised or (ii) non-parasitised bumble bees; heather pollen
129 containing either (iii) parasitised or (iv) non-parasitised bumble bees; microcolonies fed with willow pollen
130 supplemented with extracts of flavonoids from heather pollen containing either (v) parasitised or (vi) non-
131 parasitised bumble bees. Diets (i) and (ii) were used as controls as well as to assess the parasite impacts.
132 Diets (iii) and (v) were used to establish the effects of heather pollen or its flavonoids on infected
133 microcolonies. Diets (iv) and (vi) were used to establish the effects of heather pollen or its flavonoids on
134 uninfected microcolonies. For each treatment, ten microcolonies have been established using five different

135 queenright colonies (colonies from *Biobest bvba*; Westerlo, Belgium) (2 microcolonies per colony per
 136 treatment). Colonies of the species *Bombus terrestris* were selected since this species is easy to rear and a
 137 natural forager of heather pollen (Kleijn & Raemakers, 2008; Ballantyne et al., 2015). Faeces of queenright
 138 colonies were observed under the microscope to confirm the absence of parasites (*Nosema* spp., *Apicystis*
 139 spp. and *Crithidia* spp.) as guaranteed by the supplier. The microcolonies were kept in plastic boxes (10 x
 140 16 x 16 cm; Regali & Rasmont, 1995) and reared at the University of Mons (Belgium, Mons, Campus de
 141 Nimy, WGS84 50°27'54.9"N 3°57'24.9"E) in a dark room at 26-28°C and 65% of relative humidity. Bumble
 142 bees were provided *ad libitum* with sugar syrup (water/sugar 35:65 w/w) and pollen candies (i.e., pollen
 143 mixed with a 65% sugar solution) for 35 days, with pollen candies being freshly prepared and renewed
 144 every two days. When workers died, they were discarded, weighed and replaced by a worker from the
 145 same queenright colony, which was marked with a colour dot on the scutum. Larvae ejected from the
 146 brood were also checked every day, counted and discarded from the microcolonies. Microcolonies were
 147 handled under red light to minimise disturbance.

148

149 **Figure 1. Bioassay design.** Microcolonies initiated with five *B. terrestris* workers were fed for 35 days
 150 with one of three diets. For each diet, ten microcolonies contained parasitised individuals (*Crithidia*
 151 sp.), ten others were non-parasitised. Icon used for the figure: <https://www.flaticon.com/>. and
 152 author conception.

153 **Diet preparation**

154 Willow pollen batch (i.e., pollen loads from *Apis mellifera* L. 1758) was supplied by the commercial
 155 company *Ruchers de Lorraine* (Nancy, France) while heather pollen batch was obtained from a private
 156 beekeeper (Dittlo François, France, Gironde, Le Nizan). Although honey bee collected pollen loads may
 157 contain parasites, analysis of faeces of uninfected microcolonies fed with this pollen diet were parasite
 158 free. We then consider that no contamination occurred from the pollen batch. Pollen loads from the
 159 heather batch were hand-sorted based on the colour after microscopical identification to ensure
 160 monoflorality (800 g in total) (Sawyer & Pickard, 1981; Dafni et al., 2005). Each pollen batch was then
 161 homogenised and crushed before being used for the experiments. Half of the sorted heather batch served
 162 directly for the bioassays; the other half served for massive extraction of flavonoids. Flavonoids were
 163 extracted using a Soxhlet extraction for approximately 40 cycles with methanol as solvent, at 100°C. Extract
 164 was then vacuum filtered and evaporated to dryness (rotavapor IKA RV8). For flavonoid purification,
 165 extract was solubilized in water with a minimal amount of methanol, and placed in a separatory funnel
 166 with dichloromethane. The funnel was shaken and left to settle overnight before recovering the aqueous
 167 phase. The purified extract was then dried using rotary evaporator and dissolved in aqueous ethanol

168 solution (1:1, v/v) before addition to the control diet to prepare a flavonoid-supplemented diet. Control
169 and heather pollen diets were also supplemented with a similar amount of ethanol to avoid any bias (for
170 details see Appendix A, Table S1).

171 **Parasite inoculation**

172 Multiple morphologically identical trypanosomes affect *B. terrestris* (Bartolomé et al., 2021). Although
173 *Crithidia bombi* is by far the most abundant in wild populations (Shykoff & Schmid-Hempel, 1991; Popp et
174 al., 2012), parasite identification will be limited to *Crithidia* sp. in this manuscript to avoid
175 misinterpretation. Parasite inoculation was performed using *Crithidia* sp. reservoirs maintained in the
176 laboratory (i.e., commercial colonies regularly renewed and repeatedly inoculated with contaminated
177 faeces in order to ensure a turnover of the available *Crithidia* sp. pool). Faeces from a total of 45 infected
178 workers were collected and pooled together to ensure multiple-strain inoculum (Gekière et al., 2022a).
179 The inoculum was homogenised, brought to 1 mL with 0.9% NaCl solution, and purified by a triangulation
180 method (Cole, 1970) adapted by Baron et al. (2014) and Martin et al. (2018). The concentration of *Crithidia*
181 sp. cells was then estimated by counting with a Neubauer chamber, and the inoculum was diluted to 2,500
182 *Crithidia* sp. cells/ μ L with a 40% sugar solution. Workers allocated to the infected microcolonies were
183 placed in individual Nicot[®] queen rearing cages and given 10 μ L of the inoculum (i.e., 25,000 *Crithidia* sp.
184 cells; Logan et al., 2005) by letting them feed on the sugar solution in a glass microcapillary after a 5-hour
185 starvation period. Workers allocated to uninfected microcolonies also underwent the same treatment
186 (isolation, starvation) but with 10 μ L of sterile sugar solution.

187 **Parameters evaluated**

188 To investigate the impacts of pollen diet and parasite, several parameters in microcolonies were
189 measured (Tasei & Aupinel, 2008), namely resource collection, reproductive success, stress response, and
190 individual health through fat body content (i.e., immunocompetence proxy; Arrese & Soulages, 2010;
191 Rosales, 2017; Vanderplanck et al., 2021) and parasite load measurements.

192
193 Resource collection was assessed by weighing every two days in each microcolony the syrup container,
194 as well as the recovered pollen candy and the newly introduced one. These data were corrected for
195 evaporation using controls, as well as divided by the total worker mass by microcolony to avoid bias due
196 to worker activity. To evaluate the reproductive success, all microcolonies were dissected at the end of the
197 experiment (Day 35) to weigh the total hatched brood mass, as well as the individual mass of each emerged
198 male used as reference of viable offspring at the end of development (Goulson, 2010). Offspring masses
199 were divided by the total worker mass by microcolony to avoid any bias due to worker care. Regarding
200 stress response, we assessed worker mortality, larval ejection, pollen dilution (ratio between the collection
201 of syrup and pollen) as well as pollen efficiency (ratio between offspring mass and pollen collection; Tasei
202 & Aupinel, 2008) that highlights when a micro-colony needs to consume more pollen to produce offspring.
203

204 For the individual health parameters, fat body content was measured at the end of the bioassays on
205 two males and two workers per microcolony (40 individuals per treatment) following Ellers (1996). The
206 abdomens were cut and dehydrated in an incubator at 70°C for three days before being weighed. They
207 were then placed for one day in 2mL of diethyl ether to solubilise lipids constituting the fat body. The
208 abdomens were then washed twice with diethyl ether, and incubated at 70°C for seven days before being
209 weighed. Fat body content was defined as the mass difference between dry abdomen before and after
210 lipid solubilisation, divided by the dry abdomen mass prior to solubilisation. Moreover, in infected
211 treatments, we repeatedly monitored the parasite load within microcolonies using the same marked
212 worker along the bioassays. The first measurement was made three days post-inoculation (day 4) to enable
213 *Crithidia* sp. to multiply and ensure its presence in the faeces (Logan et al., 2005). A total of seven further
214 measurements were taken to establish the infection curve of *Crithidia* sp., namely on days 6, 8, 10, 12, 16,
215 20 and 35. Measurements were performed at larger intervals after day 12 because infection reached the
216 plateau phase (Schmid-Hempel & Schmid-Hempel, 1993; Otterstatter & Thomson, 2006). In practice, the
217 marked worker was held in a 50mL Falcon in the light until the faeces were expelled. Faeces were then
218 collected in a 10 μ L microcapillary tube and diluted two to ten times with distilled water to enable rational
219 cell counting. Parasite cells were then counted using a haemocytometer (Neubauer) under an inverted

220 phase contrast microscope (400X magnification, Eclipse Ts2R, Nikon). Uninfected microcolonies faeces
221 were checked to be free of parasites at the end of the experiment, and a marked worker was isolated at
222 days 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 16, 20 and 35 in each uninfected microcolony to induce the same stress as in infected
223 treatments.

224 **Data analysis and statistics**

225 To detect a potential effect of pollen diet or parasite on resource collection, reproductive success,
226 stress response, and individual health, mixed models were fitted for each parameter using diet, parasite
227 and their interaction as fixed factors, and colony as random factor. Pollen collection, pollen efficacy, and
228 pollen dilution (log-transformed data) were analysed using a Gaussian distribution (i.e., normality of
229 residuals; *shapiro.test* function from the stats R-package v.4.1.0; R Core Team, 2021) (*lmer* function from
230 the nlme R package v.3.1.160; Pinheiro et al., 2022). Total hatched offspring mass, emerged male mass,
231 and fat body content (i.e., proportion data) were analysed using a Gamma distribution and a log link
232 function (*glmmTMB* function from the glmmTMB R-package v.1.1.4; Brooks et al., 2017). For fat body
233 content, values were square root-transformed and sex was added as crossed-fixed effect. For emerged
234 male mass and fat body content, microcolony was nested within colony in the random factor to deal with
235 pseudo-replication (i.e., several measures per microcolony).

236
237 For larval ejection, a binomial distribution (ejected larvae and total number of living offspring produced
238 as bivariate response) was used after checking for overdispersion and zero inflation (*testDispersion* and
239 *testZeroInflation* functions from DHARMA R-package v.0.4.6; Hartig, 2022). For worker mortality, a Cox
240 proportional hazard (mixed-effect) model was run with individuals alive at the end of the 35-day treatment
241 assigned as censored, and those who died as uncensored (*coxme* function from the coxme R-package
242 v.2.2.18.1; Therneau, 2022). For these two parameters, diet, parasite and their interaction were also used
243 as fixed factors and colony was included as a random factor.

244
245 The last parameter measured was the parasite load at different time points within infected
246 microcolonies. As infection dynamics is a discrete time series, it was analysed using a generalised additive
247 mixed-effect model (GAMM; Wood, 2006). Parasite loads were square root-transformed and fitted using
248 a Gaussian distribution with a log link. Diet and day were set as fixed factors and microcolony nested within
249 colony as random factors. The model assumptions were tested using diagnostic graphs and tests.

250
251 Contrasts were then performed on the models to determine whether the uninfected control differed
252 from the infected control, and whether effects on uninfected or infected microcolonies differed among
253 diets (*emmeans* function from the emmeans R-package v.1.8.2; Lenth, 2022). For fat body content, data
254 were analysed separately for workers and males as a sex-significant effect was detected. Graphs and plots
255 were all performed using the R-package ggplot2 v.3.4.0 (Wickham, 2016) except the one referring to the
256 survival probability of the workers performed with the *ggsurvplot* function of the survminer R-package
257 v.0.4.9 (Kassambara et al., 2021). All the statistical analyses were done using the R software v.4.1.0 (R Core
258 Team, 2021). For all statistical analyses, $p < 0.05$ was used as a threshold for significance.

259 **Results**

260 **Parasite impact**

261 Comparison of microcolonies fed with control pollen between parasitised and non-parasitised
262 treatments showed that *Crithidia* sp. infection did not impact the parameters related to resource collection
263 (Fig 2A), reproductive success (Fig 2B-2C), or stress response (Fig 3A-C) ($p > 0.05$, Fig. 2 and 3). However,
264 fat body content in newly emerged males was significantly higher with a mean that increased by 56% in
265 infected microcolonies fed the control diet compared to uninfected ones fed the same diet ($t = -3.828$, $p =$
266 0.0012 ; Fig. 4B). The estimates (mean \pm standard error) of our variables for each treatment are available in
267 the appendices (Appendix B, Table S2)

268

269 **Effect of heather pollen and its flavonoids on healthy bumble bees**

270 Regarding resource collection, total pollen collection was significantly lower in microcolonies fed the
271 supplemented diet compared to those fed the other diets (control vs supplemented: 43% less pollen
272 collected, $t = -5.672$, $p < 0.001$; heather vs supplemented: 33% less pollen collected, $t = 3.924$, $p < 0.001$;
273 Fig. 2A). With regards to the reproductive success, microcolonies fed the supplemented and heather diets
274 produced a significantly lower brood mass compared to microcolonies fed the control diet (control vs
275 supplemented: brood mass 52% lower, $t = 3.890$, $p < 0.001$; control vs heather: brood mass 32% lower, $t =$
276 2.189 , $p = 0.0331$; Fig. 2B), as well as significantly smaller emerged males (control vs supplemented: $t =$
277 2.350 , $p = 0.0192$; control vs heather: $t = 2.925$, $p = 0.0036$; Fig. 2C)

278
279 In terms of stress responses, pollen dilution was significantly higher in microcolonies fed the
280 supplemented diet compared to those fed the other diets (control vs supplemented: $t = 2.282$, $p = 0.0268$;
281 heather vs supplemented: $t = -3.191$, $p = 0.0025$; Fig. 3A). Microcolonies fed the heather or supplemented
282 diets also displayed a lower pollen efficacy than the microcolonies fed the control diet (control vs
283 supplemented $t = -2.741$, $p = 0.0085$; control vs heather: $t = -3.025$, $p = 0.0039$; Fig. 3B). On the contrary,
284 no significant difference was detected for larval ejection ($p > 0.05$) or for worker mortality ($p < 0.05$, Fig.
285 3C).

286
287 Regarding individual health, while no difference was detected in worker fat body content among diet
288 treatments ($p > 0.05$; Fig. 4A), fat body content in newly emerged males was significantly higher in
289 microcolonies fed the supplemented or heather diets compared to those fed the control diet (control vs
290 supplemented: fat body content 62% higher, $t = -3.891$, $p = 0.0012$; control vs heather: fat body content
291 41% higher, $t = 2.850$, $p = 0.0223$; Fig. 4B).

292 **Effect of heather pollen and its flavonoids on parasitised bumble bees**

293 Similarly to previous results with uninfected microcolonies, total pollen collection was significantly
294 lower in infected microcolonies fed the supplemented diet than in microcolonies fed the control diet (36%
295 less pollen collected, $t = -4.414$, $p < 0.001$), but also in infected microcolonies fed heather diet compared
296 to those fed the control diet (16% less pollen collected, $t = -2.866$, $p = 0.0061$) (Fig. 2A). Regarding the
297 reproductive success, as observed in uninfected microcolonies, microcolonies fed the supplemented and
298 heather diets produced a significantly lower brood mass compared to microcolonies fed the control diet
299 (control vs supplemented: brood mass 51% lower, $t = 3.784$, $p < 0.001$; control vs heather: brood mass
300 41% lower, $t = 3.551$, $p < 0.001$; Fig. 2B). However, no significant difference was detected for the mass of
301 newly emerged males among diet treatments ($p < 0.05$; Fig. 2C).

302
303 Regarding stress responses, pollen dilution was significantly higher in microcolonies fed the
304 supplemented diet than in microcolonies fed the other diets (control vs supplemented: $t = 2.111$, $p =$
305 0.0398 ; heather vs supplemented: $t = -2.120$, $p = 0.0390$; Fig. 3A). Microcolonies fed the heather or
306 supplemented diets also displayed a lower pollen efficacy than those fed the control diet (control vs
307 supplemented: $t = -3.684$, $p < 0.001$; control vs heather: $t = -4.904$, $p < 0.001$; Fig. 3B). While no significant
308 difference was detected for larval ejection ($p > 0.05$), the worker survival probability was significantly
309 reduced in infected microcolonies fed the heather diet compared to those fed either the control or
310 supplemented diets (heather vs control: $t = -2.265$, $p = 0.0235$; heather vs supplemented: $t = -3.331$, $p <$
311 0.001 ; Fig. 3C).

312
313 In terms of individual health, no difference was detected in fat body content of workers or newly
314 emerged males among diet treatments ($p > 0.05$; Figs. 4A and 4B). Regarding the parasite load, the infection
315 dynamic was more gradual in infected microcolonies fed the control diet compared to those fed the other
316 diets which supported a parasite load peak around day 20 before a decrease up to the end of treatment
317 (supplemented vs control: $t = 2.893$, $p = 0.0126$; heather vs control: $t = 2.328$, $p = 0.0313$; Fig. 4C).

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328 **Figure 3. Stress responses.** (A) Pollen dilution, defined as the ratio between syrup and pollen
 329 collection; (B) Pollen efficacy, defined as the ratio between total mass of hatched offspring and pollen
 330 collection; and (C) Worker survival probability over time. For (A) and (B), each coloured data point
 331 represents a microcolony, diamonds are mean values of each treatment, and error bars indicate the
 332 standard error. Letters indicate significance at $p < 0.05$ (pairwise comparisons within uninfected
 333 treatments in black, and pairwise comparisons within infected treatments in blue); *n.s.*, non-
 334 significant. Arrows indicate the pairwise comparisons for the control diet between infection
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Figure 4. Health parameters. (A) Worker fat body content, and (B) Male fat body content; each coloured data point represents a microcolony, diamonds are mean values of each treatment, and error bars indicate the standard error. Means and error bars have been shifted in the graphs to improve readability. (C) Parasitic load over time. Generalized additive mixed-effect models (in C) were used to fit smoothers to the data showing mean trends [$\pm 95\%$ confidence intervals, light coloured bands] over time. Here, each dot represents one data point (i.e., parasite load for the monitored worker for each time point and each microcolony). Letters indicate significance at $p < 0.05$ (pairwise comparisons within uninfected treatments in black, and pairwise comparisons within infected treatments in blue); n.s., non-significant; **, $p < 0.01$. Arrows indicate the pairwise comparisons for the control diet between infection treatments (i.e., parasite effect). Symbol caption is in the grey zone.

354 Parasite effect on bumble bee

355 The parasite had no impact neither on larval ejection, total mass of offspring produced, nor on
356 individual mass of newly emerged males. Such results suggest that infection is unlikely to reduce colony
357 and offspring fitness, or dissemination success, which are related to individual size (Greenleaf et al., 2007;
358 Amin et al., 2012). The limited effects of *Crithidia* sp. on the reproductive success of bumble bees herein
359 observed are in line with the literature (Brown et al., 2003; Goulson et al., 2018; Gekière et al., 2022a). This
360 absence of impacts on development performance and offspring fitness may stem from the fact that the
361 parasite only infects the adult stage (i.e., *Crithidia* sp. does not develop in bumble bee larvae, Folly et al.,
362 2017).

363

364 Besides our results showed that *Crithidia* sp. induced larger fat body content in males emerged in
365 infected microcolonies compared to those that emerged in uninfected ones, whereas it has no impact on
366 worker fat body content. We propose two rationales to explain such a *Crithidia*-induced difference in fat
367 body content only in newly emerged males and not in workers. First, newly emerged males and workers
368 were likely not inoculated at the same age. Indeed, workers developed in healthy colonies and were
369 inoculated at the adult stage (most likely > 2 days old) for the establishment of infected microcolonies.
370 However, males (most likely one day old) developed in infected microcolonies and ingested *Crithidia* sp.
371 cells upon emergence resulting in the infection of up to 90% of them (Gekière et al., 2021, *unpublished*
372 *results*). Second, while the difference in male fat body content between infected and uninfected
373 microcolonies is unlikely to have arisen from a difference in brood care (i.e., no significant difference in
374 pollen efficacy), we cannot rule out that infected workers displayed specific brood caring behaviour. For
375 instance, they could have added peculiar nutrients or microorganisms to larval food from their
376 hypopharyngeal and mandibular glands and/or stomach to prepare their offspring to face infection (e.g.,
377 addition of sterols, Svoboda et al., 1986). Such an increase in offspring fat body content through adapted
378 larval feeding by workers could be interpreted as a trans-generational prophylactic behaviour. Indeed,
379 enhanced fat body content has been assumed to correspond to a specific allocation of resources to
380 counteract parasites by mounting an immune response (Brown et al., 2003). It would be interesting to test
381 whether infected workers provide their larvae with specific central and specialised metabolites. We should
382 however underline that the relationship between fat body content and immunity has become controversial
383 since some results have been contradictory (e.g., Brown et al., 2000, Gekière et al., 2022a).

384

385 Although *Crithidia* sp. only showed mild effects in our experiment and in previous laboratory
386 experiments (Brown et al., 2003; Goulson et al., 2018; Gekière et al., 2022a), it is important to keep in mind
387 that interpretation of results observed in laboratory conditions must be interpreted with caution as
388 controlled conditions are often not representative of natural constraints encountered in the field such as
389 for instance, predation, flight, and foraging. For example, infection by *Crithidia* sp. has been shown to
390 impair pollen foraging (Shykoff & Schmid-Hempel, 1991; Otterstatter et al., 2005; Gegear et al., 2006), but
391 such effects cannot be fully comprehended under laboratory conditions.

392 Heather pollen quality: the case of flavonoids

393 Heather pollen harbours kaempferol flavonoids linked to one/two coumaroyl groups which are also
394 linked to one/two hexosides (Gekière et al., *in prep*). Herein, we have shown that these heather flavonoids
395 reduced the total offspring production, as indicated by a decreased pollen collection and a lower pollen
396 efficacy, as well as a reduced mass of newly emerged males, thereby altering microcolony performance.
397 Indeed, drone mass is known to impact flight distances, but also reproductive abilities, affecting the
398 dissemination and reproductive success of bumble bee populations (Greenleaf et al., 2007; Amin et al.,
399 2012). Such poor quality of heather pollen for the maintenance of buff-tailed bumble bee microcolonies
400 has already been pinpointed (Vanderplanck et al., 2014). While it was partly attributed to its nutritional
401 content (i.e., low concentration of amino acids and abundance of δ -7-avenasterol and δ -7-stigmasterol,
402 Huang et al., 2011, Vanderplanck et al., 2014), our study demonstrated that specialised metabolites may
403 also impact heather pollen quality, regardless of its nutritional content (i.e., central metabolites).

404

405 Both heather pollen and its flavonoids showed detrimental effects (i.e. reduction of offspring
406 production, pollen efficacy). However, heather flavonoids seemed to induce a higher stress response than
407 heather pollen as dilution behaviour was significantly higher in microcolonies fed the supplemented diet
408 compared to those fed the control diet (i.e., mixing behaviour to mitigate unfavourable diet properties,
409 Berenbaum & Johnson, 2015; Vanderplanck et al., 2018) while such a difference was not observed for
410 microcolonies fed the heather diet. The reason for this discrepancy is not obvious, as both diets harbour
411 the same flavonoids and should therefore lead to similar dilution behaviour. Two hypotheses could be
412 proposed to explain this difference: (i) flavonoids were more bioavailable in the supplemented diets
413 (outside pollen grains after the chemical extraction) and then more easily absorbed by the workers, which
414 ultimately reduced the diet palatability (Wang et al., 2019); and (ii) as flavonoid extract was added to the
415 control diet (i.e., willow pollen) that already contained flavonoids, the supplemented diet was richer in
416 flavonoids than the other diets, reaching a threshold that ultimately reduced the diet palatability.
417 Unfortunately, it is not possible to unravel these hypotheses without additional experiments. Another
418 observation supporting the potential toxicity of heather flavonoids is the increase in fat body content in
419 males emerging from microcolonies fed heather and supplemented diets compared to those emerging in
420 microcolonies fed the control diet. Indeed, such an increase could be interpreted as a specific allocation of
421 resources to the fat body for performing a detoxification activity (Li et al., 2019). In that way, flavonoid
422 assimilation is known to induce the activation of defence mechanisms based on cytochrome P450
423 monooxygenase, a molecule that is highly active in the fat body (Scott et al., 1998). This increase in fat
424 body content was not observed in workers, which could be explained by the different exposure to
425 flavonoids during their life stages. Indeed, workers within microcolonies mainly fed on syrup, while males
426 fed on pollen during their whole larval development and were then more exposed to specialised
427 metabolites. Moreover, it is highly possible that sensitivity to pollen-specialised metabolites is higher in
428 larvae than in adults, as already demonstrated in honey bees (Lucchetti et al., 2018).

429 **The complex response of parasitised bumble bees to heather pollen and its flavonoids**

430 Flavonoids were associated with an increase in parasite load, which has been also observed for other
431 classes of specialised metabolites (Thorburn et al., 2015; Gekière et al., 2022a). Therefore, by contrast to
432 our expectations based on previous studies (Baracchi et al., 2015, Koch et al., 2019), the detrimental effects
433 of heather pollen flavonoids on bumble bees were not balanced by any therapeutic effect against the
434 parasite *Crithidia* sp. These results suggest a potential additive effect between phytochemical and parasite
435 stress as previously described (Thorburn et al., 2015), with the diet effect mostly overriding the parasite
436 effect in bumble bees in the case of heather as already shown for the sunflower (Gekière et al., 2022a).
437 The nutritional stress due to heather pollen feeding could then increase the effect of *Crithidia* sp. which
438 could be more effective under stressful conditions (Brown et al., 2000; Brown et al., 2003).

439
440 We found that mortality in infected microcolonies was lower in microcolonies fed the heather diet
441 compared to those fed the control diet. Although infection was not shown to have a significant impact on
442 mortality in microcolonies fed the control diet, heather pollen could then increase host tolerance to the
443 parasite but this effect is unlikely due to its flavonoid content as mortality in infected workers fed the
444 supplemented diet did not significantly differ from those fed the control diet. Regarding fat body content
445 in newly emerged males, males that emerged in microcolonies fed the heather or supplemented diets
446 displayed higher fat body content than those that emerged in microcolonies fed the control diet, but this
447 diet effect was not significant anymore in infected microcolonies, probably because, as discussed before,
448 the parasitic stress also increased fat body content in microcolonies fed the control diet.

449 **Conclusion**

450 How heather pollen and its specialised metabolites impact the buff-tailed bumble bee, and how they
451 modulate the interaction with its obligate gut parasite *Crithidia* sp. are complex questions given the
452 diversity of specialised metabolites found in the floral resources of this species. Previous studies have
453 found that heather nectar does not contain any flavonoids (Gekière et al., in prep) but protected the
454 pollinator from its parasite *Crithidia* sp. through callunene activity (Koch et al., 2019). In this study, we
455 found that the occurrence of flavonoids in heather pollen reduced its collection, as well as the bumble bee

456 fitness. Moreover, heather pollen did not help to counteract the parasite but rather appeared to induce an
457 additional stress that could potentially increase the parasite effect. Actually, our results complete the
458 understanding of the bumble bee-heather-parasite relationship by underlining that heather pollen is not
459 suitable for buff-tailed bumble bee performance and does not display any therapeutic effect. This study
460 highlights the complexity of the plant-pollinator interaction by illustrating the distinct roles and effects of
461 specialised metabolites found either in nectar or pollen. We strongly encourage the consideration of these
462 two floral resources in future studies investigating the medicinal effects of plant species, especially when
463 defining pollinator conservation strategies.

464 **Acknowledgements**

465 We would like to thank D. Evrard and L. Marin for their help in colony and microcolony maintenance,
466 as well as the numerous people that helped with microcolony dissection. We are very grateful to the
467 Laboratory of Cellular Biology (UMons) and the Laboratory of Therapeutic Chemistry and Pharmacognosy
468 (UMons) for their advice and the access to the device needed for the microscope analyses and the diet
469 preparation. We also thank François Dittlo for providing us with heather pollen, as well as the family of the
470 first author (I., C., C., and C. Tourbez) for their help.

471 **Funding**

472 This study was funded by the ‘METAFLORE,2019–2023’ project, one ARC ‘Actions de Recherche
473 Concertées’ project. C.T. PhD grant is funded by the University of Mons (UMONS). A.G. is supported by a
474 F.R.S.-FNRS PhD grant ‘Aspirant’. The PhD grant of I.S. is supported by the ARC project METAFLORE.

475 **Authors’ contributions**

476 Conceptualization, M.V.; chemical analyses and extraction, I.S. and P.G.; bioassays, C.T., with help from
477 A.M. and A.G.; resources, D.M. and P.G.; writing—original draft preparation, C.T., with help from A.G. and
478 M.V.; supervision, A.G. and M.V.; funding acquisition, D.M., P.G. and M.V. All authors have read and agreed
479 to the published version of the manuscript.

480 **Conflict of interest disclosure**

481 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in
482 relation to the content of the article.

483 **Data, script, and code information availability**

484 Datasets and R script are available on a Zenedo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7804841>

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Appendix A – Supplemented diet

739 Total flavonoid content of heather bee pollen, as well as its associated dried extract, were analysed in
 740 triplicates by HPLC-MS/MS (triplicates of 20 – 40 mg) for quantification (expressed as quercetin equivalent,
 741 QE). Based on these analyses, the supplementation formula was established to have a similar amount of
 742 ethanol and willow pollen in candies for all diets, as well as flavonoid concentrations in the supplemented
 743 diet mimicking natural concentration found on average in bee pollen candies, namely 12.08 mg QE/heather
 744 candy on average (14.73 ± 1.69 mg QE/g for heather bee pollen) (Table S1). We found that heather bee
 745 pollen extract contained 40.63 ± 0.72 mg QE/g (209.79 g extract).

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Table S1. Diet compositions.

Diets	Ethanol ($\mu\text{L/g}$ candy)	Pollen (g/g candy)	Flavonoids (mg/g candy)
Control diet	17.02	0.68	11.89
Heather pollen-supplemented diet	19.80	0.67	11.85 ¹
Heather diet	20.50	0.82	12.08

747 ¹ The concentration indicated for supplemented diets does not take into account the flavonoid
 748 concentration already present in the control diet (11.89 mg/g candy).

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Appendix B – Variable estimates

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Table S2. Mean \pm standard error (SE) values of the variable used to describe parasite and diet effects.

Variable	Uninfected			Infected		
	Control	Supplemented	Heather	Control	Supplemented	Heather
Pollen collection	12.7 \pm 1.21	7.27 \pm 0.85	11.0 \pm 0.67	11.7 \pm 0.70	7.53 \pm 0.81	9.01 \pm 1.01
Total mass of hatched offspring	7.16 \pm 0.58	3.43 \pm 0.46	4.87 \pm 0.40	7.04 \pm 0.36	3.46 \pm 0.50	3.64 \pm 0.67
Individual mass of emerged drone	0.259 \pm 0.005	0.213 \pm 0.006	0.201 \pm 0.007	0.252 \pm 0.005	0.226 \pm 0.009	0.215 \pm 0.006
Pollen dilution	6.14 \pm 0.40	8.08 \pm 1.00	5.58 \pm 0.34	6.29 \pm 0.37	7.87 \pm 0.61	6.62 \pm 0.86
Pollen efficacy	0.581 \pm 0.030	0.459 \pm 0.038	0.447 \pm 0.032	0.605 \pm 0.022	0.442 \pm 0.032	0.388 \pm 0.037
Larval ejection	0.984 \pm 0.006	0.970 \pm 0.010	0.999 \pm 0.001	0.969 \pm 0.007	0.889 \pm 0.053	0.990 \pm 0.007
Worker fat body content	0.131 \pm 0.008	0.159 \pm 0.009	0.147 \pm 0.006	0.138 \pm 0.007	0.166 \pm 0.009	0.131 \pm 0.006
Male fat body content	0.119 \pm 0.016	0.193 \pm 0.022	0.168 \pm 0.020	0.186 \pm 0.017	0.213 \pm 0.021	0.173 \pm 0.021

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